

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab

ESIL Stars Program Cohort 1 2023

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Introduction

The ESIL Stars Program aims to build a cohort of highly sought-after professionals who can efficiently harness emergent data and tools to address societal challenges, support data-driven decision-making and planning, accelerate scientific discovery and innovation, and bridge the data-to-knowledge gap. The ESIL Stars Program invites students from diverse backgrounds at schools serving communities that are historically underrepresented in STEM to participate in 6-months of Earth and Environmental Data Science (EDS) training and internship. Inspired by Earth Lab's Earth Data Science Corps (**IRB Protocol 20-0254**), ESIL Stars includes a combination of online data skills training for students and faculty, career-focused webinars, an open textbook that introduces novel analytics for environmental data, and project-based learning. Faculty training builds capacity to teach Earth and Environmental Data Science at partner institutions.

Student-focused goals of the program	Instructor-focused goals of the program
Encourage Student Persistence in STEM Through Earth and Environmental Data Science Career Development	Grow Earth and Environmental Data Science Teaching Capacity Through Instructor Training
Build Applied Earth and Environmental Data Science Skills	Develop Earth and Environmental Data Science Curriculum Capacity
Provide Mentorship & Community Support	Make Earth and Environmental Data Science Universally Accessible Through Open Education

This evaluation summarizes the findings from Year 1 of the ESIL Stars program at the University of Colorado Boulder. The ESIL Stars Program taught undergraduates from communities traditionally underrepresented in STEM skills at the intersection of data and Earth and Environmental science. The study assessed the ESIL Stars program’s effect on student skill attainment and development, student self-confidence, student career interest, and student career persistence in STEM to understand progress toward the intended goals of the program. In addition the study sought to understand how the online learning environment and teaching approaches supported student learning and engagement in EDS.

The program included a suite of activities to empower students to pursue Earth and Environmental Data Science jobs and build sustainable Earth and Environmental Data Science educational programs at partner institutions. During the spring (March-May), faculty and students from each institution attend a series of data science workshops hosted by ESIL, aimed at teaching the foundations of Earth and Environmental data science. In the summer semester, students and faculty applied the scientific programming skills they have learned to a hands-on project through an immersive internship experience. Throughout the program there are peer and professional career development webinars and workshops on topics such as scientific communication, working in environmental data science, and building a professional online presence. All project educational materials are shared on Earth Lab's [open education portal](#) and [YouTube](#) channel.

Questions Investigated

The research questions of the study are as follows:

1. What are effective approaches, and critical components, that help build career persistence, and increase self-confidence, science identity, and sense of belonging in Earth and Environmental data science for historically underrepresented groups in STEM?
2. How does participation in the ESIL Stars program contribute to long-term career persistence in Earth and Environmental data science for the general student population and for historically underrepresented groups? What factors of an immersive Earth and Environmental data science program lead to students pursuing careers in Earth and Environmental data science?
3. Does the proposed instructional sequence for the program lead to the development of student critical thinking skills, problem-solving, and “super skills” in Earth and Environmental data science?
4. What are effective approaches, and critical components in those approaches, for teaching and learning Earth and Environmental data science in an online format?
5. What are the success factors and challenges in learning Earth and Environmental data science in an online environment?

Executive Summary

Evaluation Findings

Students noted a **strong sense of belonging** to the science community, **identified more as an Earth and Environmental data scientist** upon completion of the program.

Students expressed **increased confidence and comfort** in their technical skill development (e.g. coding, Python-specific skills) as well as increased confidence and comfort in cross-cutting skills such as knowing how to approach a research question and communicating their research findings.

Students have a more **nuanced understanding for what Earth and Environmental data scientists do and where they work** after completing the program.

Students came into the program with a **strong interest in gaining EDS skills** and had interest in **applying these skills to their degree programs** by the end of the program. Most students indicated that they would **consider a career in EDS**.

Found the **collaborative and supportive ESIL stars environment** to be one of the best parts of the program. Students identified the **ability to work in teams** as an important skill they gained from the program.

The majority of students did not have a preference for online or in-person instruction and found advantages and disadvantages to both modes of instruction. Overall, the students **appreciated the flexibility** that the online program offered.

*"Collaboration" by Eko Purnomo, "Network" by Desi Aulia, "Network" by Iakonicon, "Organization" by Soremba, "Research" by Eucalyp, "Communication" by Creative Stall pk, "connected" by Travis Avery, "summit" by Kemesh Maharjan np all from the [Noun Project](#).

Suggestions for Program Improvement

- **Provide more scaffolding of content in the early notebooks** for those students who are coming in with no prior coding experience (e.g. introduce basic terminology and coding functions). The lack of coding experience also made using GitHub initially difficult.
- **Develop communication norms** at the beginning of the program to help facilitate collaboration. First-time interns were unsure of what to expect in terms of response times from advanced interns and mentors when they posed questions.
- The transition to GitHub was difficult for this year's participants. Some noted being more familiar with colab (or at least found colab to be more intuitive) and suggested that the program **start with colab and transition to GitHub** as students become more familiar with coding.
- Advanced interns suggested that teams that live in proximity to one another could **meet in-person on occasion**. Some students felt that others might not express themselves freely on email or slack, but with an opportunity to meet even once in person could help to make the online communication more personable.
- Advanced interns would like **more clearly defined roles and expectations** communicated at the beginning of the program. One AI perceived that not all advanced interns contributed equally to the program. Another thought that advanced interns should be there to assist but not necessarily to lead presentations.
- Faculty found difficulty connecting the knowledge gained from the previous program (EDSC) to the ESIL Stars program. Perhaps find ways to **bridge the knowledge to help returning faculty** with implementation. They missed the **regular meetings** between faculty and the program leaders.
- Faculty suggested that students have **more time to practice and learn python fundamentals** early in the program. They felt that the notebooks needed more explanation for students coming in with no prior knowledge.

Methods

The study received IRB approval from the University of Colorado, Boulder (Record # 23-0061) to examine student and faculty experiences and learning outcomes in the ESIL Stars program. Pre- and post-program surveys were designed to document student and faculty experiences, and both groups were invited to participate in group interviews at the culmination of the program.

Using a mixed methods approach, descriptive statistics and statistical tests (Wilcoxon signed-rank test or Rasch analysis when applicable for analyzing categorical data) were conducted for quantitative data; and thematic analysis was conducted for interviews and written responses to open-ended questions.

ESIL Stars Participants

A total of twenty students from participated in the ESIL Stars program. Of those twenty, nine of them were returning as Advanced Interns for the program. First-time students (all undergraduates) were affiliated with three different institutions and six faculty joined the program as well, with two faculty representing each of the three institutions. All first-time students and faculty participating in the ESIL Stars program consented to participate in the evaluation study.

First-time Student Interns in the 2023 Cohort

4 Metropolitan State University of Denver (MSU) students	N=11 Students in the 2023 Cohort
4 Oglala Lakota College (OLC) students	
3 United Tribes Technical College (UTTC) students	

Number of Responses for Survey Instruments Administered 2023

March 2023	August 2023	Aug-Sept 2023
Pre-program Survey	Post-program Survey	Interviews and Focus Groups (First-time Interns and Faculty Only)
n = 13 first-time student interns [#] n=7 advanced interns n= 5 faculty	n = 10 first-time student interns n=6 advanced interns n=5 faculty	n = 4 interns n=3 faculty

** Sample sizes for each survey represent students who consented to participate in the study. #Two interns dropped from the program leaving the final total of first-time student interns at 11 total.*

The pre-program survey collected demographic information from students (both first-time and advanced interns – See table) and faculty such as race and ethnicity, gender identity, first in their family to attend college, enrollment status, and degree pursuing. It also included questions related to program expectations, concerns, interests, awareness, EDS skills, career goals and experience with online learning.

The majority of the ESIL stars student participants identified as women (75%) and over a third of participants (7 of 20) identified as LGBTQ+. The majority of participants were American Indian or Alaska Native (65%) and nearly half of the student participants (45%) were the first in their families to attend college. The majority of participants (70%) were pursuing bachelor’s degrees and two-thirds of them were enrolled full time. Over a third of the students were pursuing degrees in computer science, GIS or Information Technology (35%) with another third (30%) pursuing degrees in Environmental Science. Over half of the students (62%) indicated that they had life commitments outside of school and work that they attended to but that those commitments did not affect the number of course credits they were taking for their degree.

Student Demographic Information (First-time (n=13[#]) and Advanced Interns (n=7))

Gender Identity*		Race and Ethnicity*	
Woman	75%	African American or Black	10%
Man	25%	American Indian or Alaska Native	65%
Non-binary	<1%	Hispanic, Latinx or Spanish Origin	20%
Gender conforming	<1%	White	45%
Self-describe	<1%	Degree Pursuing*	
First In Family to Attend College		Associate's	20%
Yes	45%	Bachelor's	70%
No	55%	Certificate	10%
Enrollment Status (First-time Interns Only)		Master's (Advanced Interns ONLY)	25% of Advanced Interns
Full time	77%	Life commitments outside of school or job (First-time Interns Only)	
Part time	23%	Yes, those commitments require me to take fewer course credits	15%
Field of Study		Yes, but those commitments do not require me to taking fewer course credits	62%
Engineering, Physics	20%	No, I don't have commitments that affect the number of credits I take	23%
Environmental Science	30%		
Computer Science, GIS, Information Technology	35%		
Ecology, Biology	15%		

*Indicates respondent could respond to more than one response option. Percentages calculated over the total respondents. #Two interns dropped from the program leaving the final total of first-time student interns at the end of the program at 11.

Findings about Science Identity and Belonging

Did students develop a science identity and a sense of belonging in science?

The study aimed to understand any programmatic effects on student identity and sense of belonging in science. Questions asked in the survey at the end of the program were taken from a validated instrument used to measure science identity and belonging (Chemers et al, 2011). At the end of the program, students responded retrospectively and were asked to reflect on their feelings after the program compared to before.

When comparing their feelings of belonging before the program and upon completion of the program, the students (both first-time interns and advanced interns), students indicated that they **felt a strong sense of belonging to the science community** (60% agreed or strongly agreed with this sentiment before the program and 87% agreed or strongly agreed by the end) (a significant change from pre- to post-program $Z=2.2$, $p=0.03$). A more subtle shift is seen with respect to the students' **feelings of belonging to the field of science**, with a third of students agreeing or strongly agreeing with this sentiment before the program (74%) but dropping to 67% after the program. The number of students strongly disagreeing or disagreeing with feeling like they belonged to the field of science decreased after the program, but more students were neutral in their feelings about belonging to the science field (from 7% before to 27% after the program).

With respect to science identity, 60% of students strongly agreed or agreed with the statement that **being a scientist is important to who they are** prior to the entering the ESiIL Stars program and increased to 80% strongly agreed or agreed with that statement after the program (a significant change from pre- to post-program $Z=2.2$, $p=0.03$). In general, students felt that **being a scientist was an important part of their self-image** both before (60% agreeing or strongly agreeing with this statement) and after (87% agreeing or strongly agreeing with this sentiment) ($Z=2.2$, $p=0.03$). There was a large shift in the sentiment of **"thinking of myself as a scientist"**, with 60% agreeing or strongly agreeing with this before the program and 87% agreeing or strongly agreeing with this after the program ($Z=2.2$, $p=0.03$).

*post-program survey

When asked to describe the overlap of their self-image with that of an Earth and Environmental data scientist, first-time interns and advanced interns alike noted increased science identity upon completion of the program. Taken together, first-time interns' and advanced interns' reported changes to their science identity were statistically significant (Wilcoxon-Pratt Signed Rank Test indicate $Z=3.2$ and $p=0.001$).

Before the program, about half of the first-time intern respondents saw very little overlap in terms of their self-image and that of an ED scientist. After the ESIL stars program, **all of the respondents indicated that the overlap between self-image and that of an Earth and Environmental data scientist was at least half or greater** (responses 4-7). Forty-four percent of the students at the end of the program saw a lot of overlap with their self-image and image of EDS (response 6). (See figure below)

*post-program survey

Students described that while they may have had interest in EDS before and perhaps were aware of basic EDS concepts, they came away from the experience with a greater understanding of the tools needed to do EDS and greater confidence in their abilities to use those tools. Those with no experience coming in, came away with greater knowledge and those with some prior experience noted development of their skills and a renewed interest in the discipline. Many indicated that they would need more training to feel fully confident in their EDS knowledge and skills.

First-time intern: *I chose three [small overlap in EDS] as the before selection because I feel like I understood some basic concepts of earth data science and therefore did not consider myself really a part of the community. Now that I've completed this program, I feel that I can say I know enough to claim to be a part of the community, but I'm not sure I would consider myself an earth data scientist just yet.*

Advanced interns (n=4) saw more overlap between their self-image and one of an Earth and Environmental data scientist coming into the program (50% indicated significant overlap), but it became more confident with their participation in the ESIL Stars program. By the end of the program, 75% (3 of the 4 advanced interns) saw nearly 100% overlap in their self-image and that of an ED scientist.

*post-program survey

Advanced Intern: *I feel like last summer was an entry point for me and my interest in EDS. Now that I have another summer and more experience, it kind of solidified my perception of myself and EDS. I feel like I can confidently call myself an Earth Data Scientist at this point in time.*

How did students develop a sense of belonging?

Understanding if students felt a sense of belonging in the ESIL Stars was an important part of comprehending underlying factors that affect student self-confidence and potentially student career persistence in related fields. During post-program interviews with first-time interns (n=4), students were asked if they felt they belonged in the program. The students indicated that **they did feel “out of place” in terms of their experience at the beginning of the program** and thought that they might not be able to do what was asked of them in the internship. **But with time and encouragement from the CU instructors, they felt more confident** and were able to put together a good project by the end.

When asked if their feelings of belonging changed with time, one intern said “ I don't know if it fully changed. I kind of feel like it's still kind of...I don't know, like imposter syndrome. Like, I don't know if I'm... meant for this field, but, ...I think what helps that is just...[that] I enjoy challenges, so I like trying to learn more about it and trying to get to that place where I feel comfortable and like I can contribute to the conversation more.”

Another student noted feeling like they did not belong because of their race and ethnicity. They knew that the program was recruiting Native students and they felt that they weren't “deserving” of their acceptance to the program because they were not Native American. The other student in the interview helped this student see that they were deserving because of the diversity they brought from their lived experience (aside from their race). It is unclear whether their perceptions of recruitment were from discussions with faculty from their own institution or whether they perceived the focused recruitment from the recruitment flyer from ESIL.

Findings about Career Persistence

An outcome of the ESIL Stars program aimed for students in the program to develop an interest in Earth and Environmental data science career tracks, or to change their career track toward Earth and Environmental data science. For the purposes of program evaluation, we asked participating students questions in surveys and interviews about awareness of, interest in, and intent to pursue careers related to Earth and Environmental data science.

Awareness of the Field of Earth and Environmental Data Science

Did students become more aware of the Earth and Environmental data science field?

The study analyzed and compared responses to the open-ended question on pre- and post-surveys which asked, “Please describe the type of work you think an Earth and Environmental data scientist does, and where they work.” The analysis looked for words that described Earth and Environmental Data Science-related fields and careers, and the degree of detail and specificity in written descriptions. Greater detail and specificity in the description would indicate a greater level of knowledge about related fields and careers. Student responses from before and after the program indicate that most

students named analyzing data as a key component of what Earth Data Scientists do. After the program some students also placed emphasis on the hard work scientists do. After the program more students named “Anywhere” or “Everywhere” as where Earth Data Scientists can work (See table below).

Type of Work Earth Data Scientists Do			Where Earth Data Scientists Work		
	Before n = 13	After n = 9		Before n = 12	After n = 9
Collects/ Analyzes Data	13	5	Everywhere	0	3
Many Research Roles/Areas	4	3	Academia/ University	2	1
Visualizes/ Communicates Data	3	4	Computer/ Research Lab	6	2
Works with Environmental Data	8	1	In the Field	3	4
Hard Work!	0	2	Private Sector	3	1
*A single student response can be categorized into multiple categories			Office	2	1
			Government	2	1
			At Home	1	1
			Non-Profit	1	1

Interest in the Earth and Environmental Data Science Field

Did student interest in Earth and Environmental data science increase?

Coming into the program, students were asked about their interest in learning more about Earth and Environmental data science. Several themes came through in the first-time intern responses, including their interests in:

- Making sense of **large datasets**
- Learning about a **new discipline, new software**
- Considering how to **apply new knowledge** to environmental problems, how to **incorporate EDS into earth and environmental science disciplines**
- **Applying** new knowledge to place-based projects
- Preparing for an **EDS career** (coding skills, python specifically)
- Using EDS to **conduct research** and to **communicate** findings

- **Improving skills** needed in science and engineering fields
- **Collaborating** with students from different institutions, working remotely

Advanced interns were asked the same questions and from their responses we saw interest in several themes as well, including their interest in:

- Expanding their **knowledge and skills** sets
- Learning what can be done with **EDS data**, learning how to understand EDS data
- Using EDS to help learn more about **homelands, sustainability issues**
- Using EDS tools in **more complex** way toward career and school projects
- **Coding and communicating** with data

In general, the first-time interns had a broader set of interests coming into the program (including collaboration with others) while the advanced interns were more focused on application and skill building.

The majority of students coming into the program were pursuing bachelor's degrees in disciplines related to Computer Science, GIS and Information Technology as well as Environmental Science. Upon completion of the program, students were still focused on achieving this goal, but a handful indicated that they were planning on completing advanced and or professional degree programs, primarily within the same disciplines that they are currently pursuing. **For these interns, there appears to already be a high interest in Earth and Environmental data science coming into the program and an interest in applying it in their existing degree programs, thus the program appears to sustain their interest in EDS, but not impact their plans for future study directly.**

In the interviews with first-time interns after the program, all indicated that they would like to “**keep learning**” about EDS. One student noted that there were limited opportunities to continue the work at their institution, and it was only through internships like this one that they were exposed to EDS. Other students, who had courses at their institutions where they could apply their EDS skills, saw the opportunity to use it as part of a classroom project.

Intent to pursue an Earth and Environmental Data Science Career or Pathway

Did students intend to pursue an Earth and Environmental data science career or pathway?

The Program Met Student Expectations for Skill Building and Career Readiness

Students were asked at the beginning of the program, “How does participation in the ESIL Stars program support your career goals?” and then asked at the end of the program how the internship may have affected their career goals. The table below shows the number of responses for each thematic category. Depending on the complexity of the response, each response was coded for one or two thematic categories. When comparing responses to both questions side by side, an overlap is seen in skill building and career readiness, showing that the internship met student expectations for the program. Some new themes that emerged were that some students stated that the

experience of the **program increased their confidence and created a positive view of careers.**

Expectations for the program supporting career goals (n=20)		How the program affected career goals (n=13)
14	Skill Building/Using Programming	6
11	Career Readiness/ Research Experience	6
6	Explore Career Interests	7
*A single student response could be categorized into multiple themes		Increased Confidence: 3

Students explored and became more interested in Earth and Environmental data science careers and in opportunities to apply their new skills.

Students (first-time and advanced interns) were asked a series of questions about their thoughts on careers in Earth and Environmental data science before the program compared to after participating in the program. In general, **78% of the first-time interns and 83% of advanced interns would consider a career in Earth and Environmental data science** upon completion of the ESIL Stars program. For those who responded that they were not sure about pursuing a career in Earth and Environmental data science (n=2) at this time, they indicated the need for more knowledge and an interest in a different discipline unrelated to EDS. Students also reported having interest in working in various job sectors upon degree completion including non-profits or NGOs (n=3), government

agencies (n=2) and in the private sector doing research (n=2). A couple of students also noted not being sure about the job sector they would like to work in upon graduation.

**post-program survey*

More specifically, from their responses to a set of before and after questions we see that there is increased agreement with the sentiments related to future careers in EDS. **Over 70% of survey respondents strongly agreed that a career in EDS could be satisfying.** Over half (53%) of students strongly agreed that they could see themselves with a career in EDS and the same percentage thought that others could see them as an Earth and Environmental data scientist. Again, over half (60%) of the students strongly agreed that the steps toward a career in EDS were clear to them and 73% of students agreed or strongly agreed that they were planning for a career in EDS. **All five questions related to careers showed statistically significant increases in agreement from their feelings before the program ($Z > 2.1$, $p < 0.05$)** In fact, before the program, a few students strongly disagreed or disagreed that they could see themselves in an EDS career (7% of students) and were not planning on a future career in EDS (14% of students). By the end of the program, no students “strongly disagreed” with any of these statements related to career paths.

Findings about Skill Development

The ESIL Stars program sought to build student comfort and confidence with technical and non-technical aspects of Earth and Environmental Data Science through the combination of technical workshops and project-based learning that included an immersive Earth and Environmental data science internship. Student comfort and confidence with Earth and Environmental Data Science skills were assessed using Likert survey instruments. At the conclusion of the program, participating students were asked to complete surveys that included items designed to give students the opportunity to respond retrospectively to questions about their comfort, confidence, and agreement with prompts related to different technical and non-technical components of the workshops and internship. Here students were asked to report the level of comfort or confidence they had in a certain area prior to participating in the program and then once again after their participation was complete. Results are reported using a series of horizontal bar plots, organized by trial (BEFORE/AFTER) for easy comparison.

These findings are organized into two broad categories. The first is focused on technical skill development which includes comfort and confidence with data science generally, and programming with Python specifically. The second category explores “super skill” development, including students’ ability to communicate science findings, think critically, solve problems with data, and work collaboratively with others. This second category includes an assessment of students’ perceived ability to engage with different practices of science.

Student Technical Skill Development

Did participants develop confidence in their technical data science skills?

The ESIL Stars student participants (both first-time interns and advanced interns) had statistically significant gains in confidence in their coding skills after completing the program (see below). Before the program, over half of the students were not confident in their skills regarding writing efficient and modular code, publishing and creating reproducible workflows, and using Jupyter Notebooks and GitHub. Upon

completion of ESIL Stars, 50% or greater of the student participants noted being “very confident” in publishing code ($Z=3.2$, $p=0.002$) and “confident” in writing code ($Z=3.2$, $p=0.001$) and reproducible workflows ($Z=3.1$, $p=0.002$) as well as the use of GitHub ($Z=3.2$, $p=0.002$).

**post-program survey*

When asked about their confidence in their skills related to working with data, students came into the program with more variable confidence (see figure below). Students were the least confident in their ability to use scientific programming to work with data (43% not confident) while they were “slightly” (50%), “moderately” (14%) to “very confident” (21%) in their ability to find and access data. **After the program, the largest gains in confidence came from their ability to visualizing scientific data (86% very confident) ($Z=3.1$, $p=0.002$), half or more were “very confident” in finding and accessing data (54%) ($Z=3.2$, $p=0.002$) and drawing conclusions from data (50%) ($Z=2.8$, $p=0.005$).** Just under 50% felt “very confident” using remote sensing data and or using scientific programming (both at 43% of the student interns) ($Z=2.9$, $p=0.003$; $Z=3.2$, $p=0.001$ respectively).

**post-program survey*

Did participants develop comfort with their technical Python skills?

Across the board, the majority of participants coming into the program were not comfortable with their Python skills (see below). Across all skills, half or more of the students were “not comfortable” with any of the ten Python-specific skills used in the ESIL Stars program. **By the end of the program, the greatest gains in comfort upon completion of the program were in plotting data in Python with matplotlib and Importing text files into Python (50% felt “very comfortable”)** ($Z=3.2, p=0.001$). Just under half of the students felt very comfortable using Python to work with time series data and tabular data (43% felt “very comfortable” with both skills) ($Z=3.2, p=0.002$; $Z=3.0, p=0.002$ respectively). Comfort with working with spatial data and writing functions in Python was more mixed (57% indicating they were “moderately comfortable” with this skill) ($Z=3.0, p=0.002$; $Z=2.8, p=0.005$ respectively). There was less comfort with manipulating data in Python (majority of students indicating they were “moderately comfortable” with this skill) ($Z=3.2, p=0.001$), documenting Python code ($Z=2.9, p=0.003$), and **using loops and conditional statements (over half of the students felt “not comfortable” and “slightly comfortable” with this last skill)** ($Z=2.8, p=0.005$).

*Post-program survey

Student “Super Skills” Development

Did participants develop comfort and confidence in their general data and communication skills?

Students had a wide variety of comfort levels for different “super skills” coming into the program (see graph below). With respect to general data skills, students felt less comfortable writing code to analyze data and to document code so that others could understand and use it. They were moderately to very comfortable with using data in spreadsheets (80.4% of students) and analyzing data (67% of students). Forty-seven percent of students felt “slightly comfortable” with learning new programming languages. **By the end of the program, all of the students made statistically significant gains in their comfort with data science skills. Nearly all of the students felt moderately to very comfortable with each of the five general data skills: using spreadsheets (Z=2.4, p=0.01), analyzing data (Z=2.8, p=0.005), writing and documenting code (Z=3.3, p=0.001;**

Z=3.2, p=0.002 respectively) and learning new languages (Z=3.3, p=0.001) (93% or more of the students were comfortable with these skills).

In terms of communication skills, again, students had a variety of comfort levels coming into the ESIL Stars program. **Before coming into the program, over half of the students felt moderately and very comfortable with presenting their science ideas clearly, explaining science to non-scientists and with collaborating with others on projects.** They were less comfortable creating visuals in Python and communicating science in blog format. By the end of the program, **gains in comfort were seen across all five general communication skill categories**, particularly in **creating visuals in Python** (Z=3.3, p=0.001), **explaining their science to non-scientists** (Z=2.6, p=0.008) (60% of students felt very comfortable in both skills) and **working collaboratively** (Z=3.2, p=0.001) (73% of students felt comfortable with collaboration).

*post-program survey

Did participants develop confidence in their ability to engage with different science practices?

Students were asked to also reflect on ten prompts about their confidence in performing practices carried out by members of the science community. Similar to the findings of comfort in “super skills”, **students showed statistically significant increases in their confidence in science skills upon completing the program compared to before** (see below). **Greatest gains** could be seen in **knowing what data that you need to address a science question** ($Z=3.3, p=0.001$) and with **using scientific literature and reports** to guide research ($Z=2.9, p=0.003$) (67% very confident after the program). Over 50% of the students felt “very confident” after the program with using scientific language and terminology ($Z=2.8, p=0.005$), generating a research question ($Z=2.9, p=0.003$), addressing a research question with data ($Z=3.3, p=0.001$) and describing how data was processed as it relates to a research question ($Z=3.2, p=0.001$). **The smallest gains were in using technical science skills and communicating via blog** ($Z=3.1, p=0.002$), but even still, the majority of the students felt at least “moderately confident” in these skills upon finishing the program.

Overall Student Confidence In Earth and Environmental Data Science Skills

Rasch analysis (Boone, Staver & Yale, 2013)¹ was used to model student responses to Likert survey items, providing numerical values of item difficulty and person ability that are measured on a common ratio scale. Measures of student ability from Rasch modeling corresponding to perceived confidence, comfort, or agreement were compared across two time points (pre-program [Before] vs. post-program [After]) representing a measure of student growth in these five different areas: Science Identity, Confidence in Python and Data Science Skills, Data and Communication Skills, and Science Practices (individual questions in each dimension described in above section).

Students Show Significant Growth in Intended Program Objectives

The pre- and post-program comparison indicates growth across all five dimensions of program outcomes related to skills and identity. The greatest gain is related to specific Python skills, with smaller gains seen in the areas of data science skills,

data analysis and communication skills and science practices more generally. The smallest gain is related to science identity.

Out of fifteen undergraduate and advanced interns who answered the post survey, nine specifically mentioned python skills as a skill they learned in the program that has been of the most use to them, with thirteen total mentioning coding skills or tools (including python). Nine students also mentioned other aspects of the data process as an important skill they learned, including finding, processing, and visualizing data. Interestingly, six students discussed teamwork or collaboration as a useful skill they learned, suggesting students benefited from the program in ways outside of “resume-building” data science skills.

Findings on Student Online Learning Experiences

First-time student interns were asked before entering the ESIL stars program about their experiences with learning online. They were asked for their preference for online or in-person learning, what holds their attention and what does not, how they evaluate their progress and identify when they are falling behind. **Of the thirteen respondents, two preferred to learn online, another two preferred in-person instruction and the rest indicated that both modes had their advantages and disadvantages.** Those who preferred in-person instruction noted that it was easier to be able to feel the instructors “emotion and energy throughout the lectures”. Another noted that in-person instruction offered “dedicated time” for work and made it easier to access help. Those who preferred online learning felt that it was easier for them to focus on the work to be done, and enjoyed the flexibility and self-paced nature of the curriculum.

In learning online, students identified characteristics that **held their attention best** including: **real world video and visual** examples, **plenty of time** to go through the curriculum and review assignments as needed, working in **breakout rooms**, instructors who take their time introducing a topic and **step-by-step instructions** for reference, as well as **interactive, engaging activities** and plenty of **class discussion**. In contrast, students found that lecturing, passive listening, not enough breaks or pauses in instruction, and long periods of reading did not do a good job of keeping their attention in an online setting. Students noted the **importance of regularly feedback and acknowledgement** from the instructor, **instructor recaps** of previous lessons, completing **concrete tasks**, employing **checklists** (for assignments, deadlines), and keeping **organized** notes with completed assignments as being critical to evaluating their progression in an online class. Students felt that they would fall behind when there was not time available for questions or pauses in instruction so that students can ask for help, seeing other students progressing when others are stuck, or when the instructors move to quickly through the instructions and do not offer feedback.

When asked to describe the best parts of the ESIL Stars experience, students identified a number of activities and content that were enjoyable, including:

- Daily **collaborative work** in teams, personal **contributions to the group project**
- Discussing data with others and **working together** to analyze and visualize data
- Learning how to manipulate code, and learning what code can do/create
- Making their own github page
- **Applying their skills** to a project, using it for meaningful research, learning by doing
- The **encouraging atmosphere** from instructors and advanced interns

The theme that cut across many of these responses was the **emphasis on collaborative work and how they enjoyed the team culture**. “Working in teams” was also a skill that students identified as an important outcome of the program. All of the students indicated being “very satisfied” with the communication during the program, but slightly less so with mentors from their home institutions (3 of the 9 students indicated only being somewhat satisfied with their communication with their mentors while the other 6 were “very satisfied”).

The key takeaways that students identified from their participation in the program were that they learned so many new things (**new skills, working in teams**) that they could add to their resume, learned how **to communicate their findings** (websites, to community leaders), and saw potential for **future work** in data science and **applications** of data science to so many areas. They also noted **increased confidence and feeling empowered** upon completion of the program.

The students identified challenges to learning online as well which included **difficulty with maintaining balance** between work and school, feeling that it was a **steep learning curve** without prior experience (especially when learning python and about github), **troubleshooting** code, adjusting to **changes in team member** makeup, and learning to **format data and code syntax**.

Student interviews mirror the feedback provided in the post-program surveys, with students identifying the importance of **keeping on top of the work** from the very

beginning, that the project was both **challenging** in that they had to apply what they learned to gather and manipulate data and conduct the appropriate analyses, and **rewarding** when they saw it all come together. Students noted that instructors Nate and Elsa were **always available and willing to help** when they needed it. One student specifically called out the **video recordings** of working through the notebooks as being incredibly helpful and a good reference. Some students thought that if the program was in-person that there might be more informal ways to connect with the other interns when they were not engaged in the focus project work, but that overall, they enjoyed the **flexibility that the online program offered**.

Recommendations for Program Improvements

More scaffolding in early parts of the program for students new to coding

- Without knowing the basic python “language”, students found it difficult to work through the notebooks in the early weeks of the program. The evaluation suggests that program leaders scaffold the information a bit more in the notebooks in the first few weeks to help students get up to speed (like spending more time on basic coding terminology and functions).
- Record additional videos of instructors working through the notebooks for the start of the program. Students found these useful to watch and re-watch in order to get familiar with coding syntax and to help troubleshoot errors in their code.
- If time allows, a suggestion is to build in more time for coding practice in order for students to learn the Python basics. Faculty noted that students did not have a firm grasp at the start of the program and made it difficult for the mentors in later parts of the program (e.g. when working on the project).

Provide more detailed information related to advanced intern roles and team communication

- First-time interns noted that they were not clear about the expectation for turn-around time when it came to asking questions of the advanced interns and mentors. Setting clear communication norms at the start of the program (and a place where they can reference these norms) might help ensure all participants are on the same page.
- The role of advanced intern could be more clearly defined and the expectations more clearly stated. There was a perception that not all advanced interns were contributing equally to the student needs.

Consider additional meetups among participant groups

- While students did not have a preference regarding the mode of instruction for ESIL Stars (online vs. in-person), students suggested that in-person meetups (if possible) would help improve communication in the online environment (email and slack). This suggestion might work best for students at the same institution and was not necessarily suggested for program participants as a whole.
- Faculty noted that they missed having regular faculty meetings with program leads. They hoped that these could be incorporated next year as they work to improve implementation of the ESIL Stars material.

Conclusions

The overarching goal of the ESIL Stars program is to increase diverse participation in Earth and Environmental Data Science career pathways. To achieve this goal, the program has identified focused student support, increased confidence in skills, and greater awareness and interest in Earth and Environmental data science as key outcomes for the program. The findings identified by the evaluation indicate that students are feeling supported in the program through the welcoming and supportive environment created by the program leaders and the access to assistance from advanced interns, faculty mentors and the program leaders at CU. Students report having

an increased sense of belonging to the scientific community and credit collaboration and working in teams as important skills they are taking away from the program.

In terms of skill development, the student participants show statistically significant gains in confidence and comfort across four different dimensions: data science skills, python skills, data and communication skills as well as general science practices. Furthermore, the evaluation identified that students came away with a greater awareness for what Earth and Environmental data scientists do and where they work as well as increased interest in applying data science skills to their current degree programs and seeking graduate degrees in Earth and Environmental data science. Collectively, the findings indicate that the ESIL Stars program is laying the foundation necessary for students to find Earth and Environmental data science career pathways.

References

Boone, W. J., Staver, J. R., & Yale, M. S. (2013). *Rasch analysis in the human sciences*. Springer Science & Business Media.

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Appendix

[Pre-program survey \(for students, advanced interns, and faculty\)](#)

[Post-program survey \(for students and advanced interns\)](#)

[Post-program survey \(for faculty\)](#)